

Crop and resource management

Physiology and plant nutrition

Effect of hydroquinone and phenylhydrazine on yield and nitrogen use efficiency of rice

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This field experiment evaluated the N use efficiency (NUE) of using two urease inhibitors, hydroquinone (HQ) and 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (PH). Rice (cv Pusa 169) was grown in the wet season (June to November) of 1994. The soil was an Ustochrept clay loam with 0.45% organic C, 667 mg total N kg⁻¹, 232 kg available N ha⁻¹, 37 kg available P ha⁻¹, 291 kg available K ha⁻¹, pH 8.2, EC 0.48 dS m⁻¹. The table shows the treatments in a completely randomized block design with three replications in 5- × 4-m plots. Urea, at the rate of 120 kg N ha⁻¹, was applied in three splits: one-half at the time of transplanting, one-fourth 30 d after transplanting (DT), and one-fourth 50 DT.

The plots were basally dressed with P and Kat the rate of 26.4 and 49.8 kg ha⁻¹, respectively, and irrigated to maintain 5 cm of standing water. Residual effect was studied by growing wheat (cvHD2285) after rice harvest in the dry (December to April) season of 1994-95. A booster dose of 50 kg N ha⁻¹ was applied 40 d after sowing in all the plots. The experiment was repeated in the same site during 1995-96.

Adding either HQ or PH with urea increased yield of rice more than using urea alone in both the years (see table). In 1994-95, the highest yield (6.89 t ha⁻¹) was recorded with urea plus 10% PH, and the next highest yield (6.55 t ha⁻¹) with urea plus 10% HQ. Harvest index showed no significant difference. Application of PH at 5 and 10% and HQ at 10% with urea resulted in a higher uptake of N than with application of urea alone. The NUE increased when HQ and PH were added. With urea alone, the efficiency was 14.75 kg of grain kg⁻¹ N. It increased to 18.08 and

25.58 kg of grain kg⁻¹ N with the application of 5 and 10% of HQ and 25.25 and 28.42 kg of grain kg⁻¹ with 5 and 10% PH. Application of 10% of HQ and PH increased the N recovery by almost 60 and 100%, respectively. Total N content of the soil after harvest showed no significant difference among treatments. Residual effect of various treatments was also not significant. During 1995-96, NUE and N recovery were less than in 1994-95. Higher NUE and N recovery found in both the years with the use of HQ were attributed to reduced volatilization loss of ammonia. With the use of PH, higher NUE was attributed to increased mineralization of immobilized fertilizer N.

Although these inhibitors increased yield, NUE, and N recovery, the benefit-cost ratio (B/C) was poor. In both years, B/C was less than 1.0, indicating net economic loss. At the present price of HQ and PH, use of these chemicals in rice cannot be recommended. ■

Yield, N uptake, N use efficiency, and N recovery of rice, total N content of soil after rice, grain yield of wheat, and benefit-cost ratio (B/C) of using hydroquinone (HQ) and dinitrophenylhydrazine (PH). New Delhi. 1994/95.

Treatment	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)						Harvest index		N uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)		N (kg kg ⁻¹)							
	Rice grain		Rice straw		Wheat grain		1994	1995	1994	1995	Use efficiency		Recovery		Content in soil		B/C	
	1994	1995	1994	1995	1994	1995					1994	1995	1994	1995	1994	1995	1994	1995
Control	3.5	3.8	6.1	6.2	3.6	3.8	0.36	0.38	58.95	66.32	—	—	—	—	539.1	552.6	—	—
Urea	5.3	5.1	7.6	7.6	4.5	4.7	0.41	0.40	100.15	98.86	14.75	11.08	34.33	27.12	684.0	646.2	—	—
U + 5% HQ	5.7	5.8	8.0	7.9	4.7	4.8	0.41	0.43	111.13	108.46	18.08	17.08	43.48	35.12	633.1	654.3	0.54	0.79
U + 10% HQ	6.6	6.7	7.7	7.7	4.9	4.9	0.46	0.47	126.96	122.58	25.58	24.50	56.67	46.88	664.5	686.4	0.80	0.90
U + 5% PH	6.5	6.4	7.5	7.5	4.5	4.8	0.47	0.46	123.27	128.12	25.25	22.08	53.60	46.88	601.7	628.5	0.46	0.50
U + 10% PH	6.9	6.8	7.5	7.9	4.6	4.9	0.48	0.46	140.36	136.64	28.42	24.75	67.84	58.60	644.4	638.4	0.32	0.34
CD (0.05)	1.2	1.1	1.5	1.2	—	ns	0.09	0.07	12.84	13.46	—	—	—	—	ns	ns	—	—
CV (%)	8.5	9.2	9.7	8.8	6.6	7.8	7.4	6.2	8.7	9.4	—	—	—	—	9.5	8.6	—	—

U = urea, B/C = benefit-cost ratio (rice plus wheat), cost of PH = US\$25 kg⁻¹, cost of HQ = US\$9.4 kg⁻¹, price of rice = US\$117 t⁻¹, price of wheat = US\$125 t⁻¹.